

Two Kinds of Equilibria: Particle and Wave/Dynamic Based? Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 9, 2022

In Part I we considered two kinds of statistical processes. One is based on a scalar additive which changes in stochastic processes e.g. kinetic energy in two body elastic collisions or the spatial shell in a 3D random walk problem. We argued that in such a case, one considers $a_1+a_2= a_3$ (where a_i is the distributive scalar) and a product probability scheme i.e. $P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3)$ to find that $P(a_i) = C \exp(-a_i b)$ where b is a parameter which may be found if the average value of a is known. Furthermore, we argued that the distributive scalar process is identical to maximizing entropy subject to a constraint $\text{Sum over } i \ a_i P(a_i)$.

The second process is based on a dynamic vector changing in the stochastic process. We used the problem of light reflecting and refracting (which we argued is similar to quantum mechanics for a pure bound state) and noted that the p (momentum) vector changes i.e. an incoming p along the x axis in the positive direction becomes $-p$ on reflection or p_2 on refraction in 1 dimension. We suggested that a dynamic probability is needed in such a case, namely an eigenfunction of the generator associated with the dynamic variable, e.g. x for p . The eigenfunction is then periodic. Using $\exp(ipx)$ s (eigenfunctions of $-id/dx$) one may calculate average energy at x and fix weights i.e. $\{\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\} / \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\} + V(x) = E_n$, but there is no maximization of entropy.

At first the additive scalar (distributive variable) and dynamic vector approaches seem to be very different (for example, one maximizes entropy and the other does not), but in this note we argue there are a number of similarities. We focus on these similarities and suggest these may perhaps be key features that unite the distributive scalar approach (classical statistical mechanics, level jumping in quantum mechanics) with the dynamical vector approach (statistics of pure quantum bound state). In particular, both types of probabilities are linked with exponential functions although one is real and drops in value $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and the other is complex and periodic $\exp(ipx)$ and $P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3)$ in both cases. Also, both are eigenfunctions of generators. Thus we suggest that the similarities between the scalar additive approach (MB gas) and dynamical vector (quantum bound states) may be the key features of overall equilibrium type statistical mechanics.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics focuses strongly on the notion of entropy being maximized subject to a constraint. This process in turn is linked to a microcanonical scenario in which one considers all possible "arrangements" each with the same weight, but strictly satisfying say a particle number and total energy constraint. The maximization of energy approach is usually a canonical scenario in which average energy is conserved i.e. it relaxes the constraint of the microcanonical approach. Thus the idea of arrangements is key. As a result, classical statistical mechanics and the statistical approach used to solve for a bound state quantum wavefunction seem very different.

In Part I, we noted that the maximization of entropy subject to a constraint approach (i.e. canonical approach) actually focuses on a scalar additive variable (distributive) variable which is

changed in the stochastic process in the problem. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, this is e_i , the kinetic energy of a particle, which changes in an elastic collision. We also noted that the maximization of entropy subject to a constraint is really subject to the specific constraint:

$$\sum_i a_i P(a_i) = \text{Average}(a) \quad \text{where } a_i = e_i \text{ in an MB gas} \quad ((1))$$

Furthermore, we suggested the entire counting of arrangements and maximization of entropy subject to a constraint may be replaced with the idea of distributive variable (additive scalar) such that:

$$a_1 + a_2 = a_3 \text{ and } P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{so that } \ln(P(a_i)) = -a_i/T \quad \text{or } P(a_i) = C \exp(-a_i/T) \quad ((2b))$$

$$\text{where } 1/T \text{ is a parameter found by solving: } \sum_i a_i P(a_i/T) = \langle a \rangle \quad ((2c))$$

Thus we argued that ((2a)) and not counting arrangements should be the key idea.

We then, however, considered a different kind of statistical problem existing in the classical world, namely the reflection/refraction of light (which we claimed was identical to quantum mechanical formalism, say for a bound state). We argued that the statistical process in this case changes a dynamical vector (not an additive scalar) and so a new approach is needed, namely basing probability on the eigenfunction of the generator of the variable associated with the dynamical process i.e. for p we chose x . As a result, one uses $\exp(ipx)$ in this scenario. As a result, the two statistical mechanical approaches, one for a scalar and the other for a vector, seem very different. We, however, want to examine their similarities so that the two may fit under one umbrella.

Similarities Between the Additive Scalar and Dynamic Vector (Quantum Mechanics) Approaches

The additive scalar approach is based on ((2a)) i.e. $a_1 + a_2 = a_3$ and $P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3)$ which leads to an exponential type solution ((2b)) $P(a_i) = C \exp(-a_i/T)$ where $1/T$ is a parameter.

We note that a_i is the variable which changes in a stochastic process and that there is a loss of information namely that in terms of probabilities and products of probabilities ((2a)) holds i.e. one cannot distinguish between $P(a_1)P(a_2)$ and $P(a_3)$ or any other 2 or more pairs for which $\sum_i a_i = a_3$ and $\text{Product over } i P(a_i) = P(a_3)$.

Thus the exponential form seems to be associated with a loss of information approach rather than a counting of states.

The parameter in question, $1/T$, is fixed using: $\sum_i a_i P(a_i, 1/T) = \langle a \rangle$ with $\langle a \rangle$ being known. For example, for $a_i = e_i$, the average energy of the system is known.

In the reflection/refraction of light or quantum bound situation, a vector, namely p momentum, changes in the stochastic process. For example, a p momentum may become $-p$ upon reflection. Thus one no longer has the scalar additive approach. Rather there is dynamics and

invariance in the problem. One does not count states and maximize entropy. Rather one bases probability on the eigenvalue of the generator associated with the dynamical variable.

For the case of p momentum, we choose x as the associated variable and find $\exp(ipx)$ to be the eigenfunction of $-id/dx$. Given translational invariance in the problem, a periodic solution results.

A point we wish to stress is that $\exp(-ai/T)$ from the scalar additive (distributive variable) approach is also an eigenfunction of a generator, namely d/db where $b=1/T$. Thus both solutions are eigenfunctions of generators and exponential.

Furthermore both solutions involve the form $P(a1)P(a2)=P(a3)$ i.e. $\exp(-e1/T)\exp(-e2/T) = \exp(-(e1+e2)/T)$ and: $\exp(i p1x)\exp(i p2x) = \exp(i (p1+p2) x)$ although $p1, p2$ may be positive or negative while ei are positive. There is nevertheless, a “loss of information” in both of the product form.

A difference which occurs in the two approaches in the number of “layers” involved. In the additive scalar problem, constant average energy is the overall constraint, but ei , particle kinetic energy, is the variable which changes in the stochastic process. Thus the overall constraint variable (energy) and the stochastic variable ei are of the same form.

In the dynamical vector case, there is an overall conservation of energy, but the variable which changes is a vector namely momentum. There is the relation $E=|p|c$, but $|p|$ is the magnitude of momentum, whereas it is the vector which changes in a reflection/refraction problem. Thus in the reflection/refraction problem there are set of equations dealing with stochastic vector i.e.

$$A+B=C \quad \text{and} \quad pA - pB = p2C \quad ((3a)) \quad ((3b))$$

and a combined energy conservation equation: $pAA - pBB = p2 CC$ which is equivalent to an overall energy conservation equation: $AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2$ where $AA = \text{intensity} = n1 E c1$ where E is the photon energy, $n1$ the number of photons in the incident beam A and $c1$ the photon velocity. B and C refer to the reflected and refracted rays and AA, BB, CC show that intensity is strictly positive. Thus $((3a)), ((3b))$ deal with square root intensity.

The quantum mechanical bound system also contains the two layers. First, $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to Fermat’s principle and the conservation of momentum in the x direction. Thus this is an extra layer because for the scalar additive (distributive variable) one simply uses a parameter i.e. $1/T$ which is fixed by average energy. Here p is the stochastic variable, but x is not an arbitrary variable. It has specific physical meaning and is linked with spatial invariance and conservation of momentum in the x direction. For example, consider minimizing time in a Fermat’s refraction problem. Then $\text{time1} = \text{ray length1} / c1$ and $\text{time2} = \text{ray length 2} / c2$. The first ray moves from $(x=0, y=L)$ to $(x,y=0)$, the medium is at $y=0$ and along the x axis and the refracted ray moves from $(x,y=0)$ to $(x=L,-Y)$. Then minimizing total time with respect to x i.e. changing x yields:

$P_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2)$ where θ is measured from the x axis and $p_1 = p_{n1}$ and $p_2 = p_{n2}$. Thus d/dx the spatial generator emerges naturally and is associated with p momentum conservation in the x direction i.e. $P_1 \sin(\theta_1)$ and $p_2 \sin(\theta_2)$. Thus there are physical implications of p_x in $\exp(ipx)$. X is not simply a parameter without meaning.

The second layer appears when one tries to implement an energy constraint just as in the additive scalar (distributive variable) problem. There: $E_{\text{average}} = N \sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ is used to find T . For the quantum case, x is already known, but one uses an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ s in a bound state with weights $a(p)$ which are fixed by an energy equation instead of $1/T$. Thus:

$$p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx) / \{ \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E_n,$$

In other words, for a scalar additive (distributive variable approach) e_i is the scalar changed in the stochastic process which leads to a $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3$ scenario, but the conjugate variable to e_i is simply a parameter which may be obtained using the average energy.

For the dynamical vector (quantum mechanical) problem, momentum is the vector which changes in the stochastic process (i.e impulse hits form a potential cause p vector changes), but its conjugate vector is not simply a set of parameters. The dynamical vector is associated with possible conservation, but not in the same way as e_i 's. The dynamical vector is linked to an invariance in space and the probability is the eigenfunction of the generator of the invariant spatial variable and is taken to be periodic i.e. the space must be measured internally. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ with no parameter to be fixed. In a bound state with a certain overall energy, however, one uses an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ s with scalar weights $a(p)$, so the overall energy equation assigns scalar values to $a(p)$ with the conjugate to the stochastic vector i.e. x already being known.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics

The idea of using an additive scalar (distributive variable) or dynamical vector depends on the stochastic process present. It is not the case that classical mechanics and quantum mechanics are strictly divided. In the classical statistical mechanics of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, the additive scalar e_i (single particle kinetic energy) exists. In a quantum single particle bound state with energy levels associated with the absorption or emission of photons, the stochastic variable is again an additive scalar, namely e_i , the energy level value. Thus the distributive variable approach applies even in this quantum mechanical example and one sees the MB factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

In the case of a quantum bound state, the stochastic process involves a momentum vector being changed by an impulse hit from a potential. Thus one has an ensemble of probabilities associated with the momentum vector, but there is no notion of an elastic collision. One uses an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ i.e $\exp(ipx)$ as probability. This probability combines with terms in the potential written as a Fourier series i.e. $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the probability and one uses the ensemble in an energy conservation equation to determine $a(p)$'s.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the approach of counting arrangements and maximization of entropy subject to a constraint leads to classical statistical mechanics and quantum bound state statistics being treated as very different theories. We argue that there are in fact many key similarities.

We note first that both theories are based on the idea that $P(a_1)P(a_2)=P(a_3)$ i.e. a loss of information under product probabilities. In the case of an additive scalar theory i.e. one in which a scalar is changed in the stochastic process e.g. e_i (energy) in elastic scattering in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas one has the further equation $e_1+e_2=e_3$ and so $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ with $1/T$ simply being a parameter which may be fixed using the average energy of the system (considered to be a known) i.e. $\sum_i e_i P(e_i) = \text{average energy}$.

If a dynamical vector is changed in the stochastic process i.e. the momentum vector from impulse hits given by $V(x)$ a potential in a single particle bound state, then one again has $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_3)$ in one dimension, but one must choose the conjugate variable in a physical manner. It is not simply a parameter e.g. $1/T$. We argue it is associated with conservation of momentum and with invariance in space as p implies motion through space. Thus we choose x and use a probability which is the eigenvalue of the generator of translations in x and also periodic i.e. $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is also the eigenfunction of the generator $d/d(1/T)$, but the physical meaning may not be so clear. For a bound state then $\exp(ipx)$ is known, but $V(x)$ delivers stochastic impulse hits so one requires an ensemble with weights $a(p)$, The overall energy (also known in the MB gas) is then used not to fix $1/T$, but to fix $a(p)$ s i.e. $\{\sum_{p} p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx)\} / \{\sum_{p} a(p)\exp(ipx)\} + V(x) = E_n$.

Thus both the scalar and vector statistical theories both contain exponential probabilities e.g. $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, but the latter is periodic and the conjugate variable is physical (i.e. x) and linked with conservation of the vector p . Both probabilities, however, are linked with loss of information in a product i.e. $P(a_1)P(a_2)=P(a_3)$. Thus if this is considered the fundamental idea of a statistical equilibrium, then classical statistical mechanics and quantum bound state statistics are very similar.